

**Harmonisation within Atmospheric
Dispersion Modelling for Regulatory
Purposes**

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Proceedings

Edited by

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PREFACE

The 18th International conference on Harmonisation within atmospheric dispersion modelling for regulatory purposes (Harmo 18) continues the activities of the International Initiative on this topic, started in 1991. Readers can find extensive scientific, practical and historical information at the web site of the Harmo Initiative: www.harmo.org

The original focus of the workshops on harmonisation was on the development of dispersion models for regulatory purposes and for real-time applications in Europe, in such a way that both latest scientific findings were used and specific demands of society and regulators were met. These meetings developed into a series of high-level scientific conferences, motivated by the idea of employing the best available meteorological and air quality sciences in harmonised way to serve the needs of European citizens.

Dispersion modelling is a tool to assess the current or future impact of air pollution sources on the environment and human health. Studying dispersion requires multi-facet approaches, namely reliable meteorological forecast at high resolution able to capture the effects of complex terrain, vegetative canopies, built environments with its characteristics. It also requires the derivation and proof of robust parametrizations of the atmospheric boundary layer and exchange processes. It involves a reasonable description of a variety of sources such as those associate to transport, industries, accidental releases, deliberate releases and natural releases. It requires efficient numerics in order to run fast and able to deliver multiple scenarios. Ideally, dispersion models used for real applications implement proven parametrizations of a large number of physical and chemical processes in the atmosphere. In addition, real time data assimilation, the evaluation of model performance and the presentation of results to public and managers are now disciplines of their own.

It has been proven through the success of the Harmo conferences by now, that this forum is needed to allow scientists focused in one or several of these different topics, to work together and come up with improved and harmonised solutions. There is a variety of models – simple or complex – covering different space and time scales and different areas of applicability. The user needs to select a fit-for-purpose dispersion model that produces reliable results for a given task and also to know the uncertainties and errors associated with the model results.

There are many requirements to models for regulatory purposes. These models should be scientifically sound; validated against observations; accompanied by clear guidelines and support to ensure proper use. Constant efforts are needed to promote the good practices and eliminate the bad practices; to assure quality with respect to model development; to establish reference problems; to share experiences.

The Harmo Conferences are directed towards model developers, model users, environmental protection agencies, and environmental legislation experts. This series of conferences is different from other scientific forums because it focuses on common tools and methodologies in a broad interdisciplinary field. These conferences are natural forum for discussing modelling issues related to the European Union air quality directives. European networks such as the FAIRMODE network and COST Actions use the Harmo conferences to expose their work to a wider audience.

The Harmo conferences have a role as a forum where users and decision-makers can bring their requirements to the attention of scientists. Not only the global atmosphere is shared by all, but also the problems related with providing real-time information of accidental releases (such as Fukushima

Nuclear Power plant destruction, Island volcano eruption, forest fires, etc.) and their impacts on economy, society and environment are required by all people and institutions around the world.

More than 170 participants from 30 countries attend the 18th International conference on Harmonisation within atmospheric dispersion modelling for regulatory purposes (Harmo 18, <http://www.harmo18.eu/>), CNR Research Area, 9 - 12 October 2017, Bologna, Italy.

The Harmo conferences participants are the international scientific community that maintains the Harmo initiative, forms the committees and organizes the conferences on voluntary basis. In this way each participant is directly involved in the process of bridging knowledge to broad public and governing authorities in order to secure sustainable and higher quality of life in Europe and worldwide.

History of the Harmonisation Workshop/Conference:

- 1st Harmo workshop, Risø National Laboratory, Denmark, 1992
- 2nd Harmo workshop, Manno, Switzerland, 1993
- 3rd Harmo workshop, Mol, Belgium, 1994
- 4th Harmo workshop, Oostende, Belgium, 1996
- 5th Harmo conference, Rodos, Greece, 1998
- 6th Harmo conference, Rouen, France, 1999
- 7th Harmo conference, Belgirate, Italy, 2001
- 8th Harmo conference, Sofia, Bulgaria, 2002
- 9th Harmo conference, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, Germany, 2004
- 10th Harmo conference, Crete, Greece, 2005
- 11th Harmo conference, Cambridge, UK, 2007
- 12th Harmo conference, Cavtat, Croatia, 2008
- 13th Harmo conference, Paris, France, 2010
- 14th Harmo conference, Kos, Greece, 2011
- 15th Harmo conference, Madrid, Spain, 2013
- 16th Harmo conference, Varna, Bulgaria, 2014
- 17th Harmo conference, Budapest, Hungary, 2016

The scientific focus of Harmo 18 is on the following topics:

TOPIC 1. Model evaluation and quality assurance – model validation, model intercomparisons, model uncertainties and model sensitivities.

TOPIC 2. Environmental impact assessment: Air pollution management and decision support systems.

TOPIC 3. Use of modelling in support of EU air quality directives, including FAIRMODE activities

TOPIC 4. Parametrization of physical processes in mesoscale meteorology relevant for air quality modelling

TOPIC 5. Urban scale and street canyon modelling: Meteorology and air quality

TOPIC 6. Use of modelling in health and exposure assessments

TOPIC 7. Inverse dispersion modelling and source identification

TOPIC 8. Modelling air dispersion and exposure to accidental releases

TOPIC 9. Modelling of passive control systems (PCS) including nature-based solutions in dispersion studies

TOPIC 10. Mathematical problems in air quality modelling

TOPIC 11. Highlights of past work. Session devoted to reviews and to prominent scientists and ‘golden papers’ of the past, which have still relevance and should not be forgotten

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The Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-ISAC) aims at an integrated scientific understanding of the atmosphere and its processes, by means of a multidisciplinary approach which combines scientific and technological competences in meteorology, climate, atmospheric dynamics and composition, Earth observations and performs basic research, experimental and modelling work and impact evaluation. ISAC is the largest CNR Institute on atmospheric sciences, structured in 7 Units over the country, 7 permanent observatories, including 2 Global Stations of the Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) program of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and 2 Supersites.

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - University of Bologna founded in 1088 is known as the oldest University in the western world and with its over 84,000 students, 33 Departments, 11 Schools, 9 Research and Training Centres, 5 Campuses, 207 Degree Programmes, 52 International degree programmes and 48 PhD programmes is one of the largest University in Italy. In particular, the **Department of Physics and Astronomy (DIFA)** with its Atmospheric Physics Group promotes basic and applied research through observation and modelling of the Earth system. It has a long tradition in numerical modelling in the field of dynamic meteorology, radiative transfer, microphysics studies, air pollution dispersion and urban climate.

The Steering, Scientific and Local Committees acknowledge the cooperation of all Harmo 18 organising institutions and thanks Dr. Cristina Sabbioni, Director of CNR-ISAC, and Prof. Nicola Semprini Cesari, Director of DIFA-UNIBO, for their contribution at the Conference Opening.

The Local Organising Committee thanks Combustion Ltd., ARIANET srl-Aria Technologies SA, Lombard & Marozzini srl, and Eurelettronica ICAS for their sponsorship.

Credits: the HARMO18 website <http://www.harmo18.eu> has been created and is maintained by Fabrizio Roccato.

Wishing to all participants successful and fruitful conference and enjoyable stay in “*la dotta*” Bologna!

Bologna, October 2017

On behalf of the Local Organising Committee,

The image shows two handwritten signatures in black ink. The signature on the left is 'Silvana Di Sabatino' and the signature on the right is 'Silvia Trini Castelli'. Both signatures are written in a cursive, flowing style.

Prof. Silvana Di Sabatino, Dr. Silvia Trini Castelli